

A new method for AFM mechanical characterization of heterogeneous samples with finite thickness

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ABSTRACT

Accurate mathematical expressions have previously been derived for determining the Young's modulus of thin homogeneous samples on rigid substrates when tested using atomic force microscopy. These equations have generally been applied to determine the mechanical properties (in terms of Young's modulus) of thin biological samples bonded to rigid substrates, such as cells. However, biological materials are highly heterogeneous at the nanoscale, so their mechanical properties vary significantly with indentation depth. Consequently, a crucial question is whether these equations are mathematically valid in such cases and if they can lead to reproducible results. In this paper, a rigorous mathematical analysis is used to investigate the validity of equations derived for homogeneous samples with finite thickness when applied to heterogeneous thin samples on rigid substrates. Using the aforementioned analysis, the classical equations are modified to account for depth-dependent mechanical properties. Consequently, the depth-dependent mechanical properties of heterogeneous samples with finite thickness are characterized using appropriate functions instead of single Young's modulus values. Force-indentation data from human fibroblasts and murine breast cancer cells are processed using the method presented in this paper, resulting in accurate and reproducible results.

KEYWORDS: biomaterials, scanning probe microscopy, thin samples, substrate artifacts

1. INTRODUCTION

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) nanoindentation has revolutionized biomedical sciences by enabling the mechanical characterization of biological samples at the nanoscale [1–3]. This capability suggests that AFM could potentially facilitate early disease diagnosis, particularly in conditions like cancer, and evolve into a clinical tool [2, 4–9]. Hertzian mechanics has typically been employed for data processing, leading to results of tremendous importance over the last 2 decades [10–25]. These classic equations have been also extended for thin homogeneous samples which are tested on rigid substrates [26–29].

However, challenges remain, particularly regarding the accurate determination of the elastic (Young's) modulus of soft samples, primarily due to issues related to the high heterogeneity of materials at the nanoscale, deflection sensitivity and the calibration of the cantilever's spring constant [30, 31]. A critical issue in determining the Young's modulus of biological samples pertains to the suitability of contact mechanics models used for data analysis, given the highly heterogeneous nature of biological materials at the nanoscale [31]. In particular, Hertzian mechanics (and its extensions for thin samples) was initially derived to describe the behavior of materials that are homogeneous and isotropic [26, 31]. On the contrary, biological samples exhibit significant heterogeneity at the nanoscale, and their "Young's modulus values" can either decrease ("soften") or increase ("stiffen") with increasing indentation depth [30]. Therefore, the Young's modulus determined using Hertzian mechanics is frequently referred to as the "apparent" Young's modulus and is highly sensitive to the depth of indentation [32–34].

To derive general equations that are applicable regardless of the mechanical heterogeneity of the tested material, one can use the contact stiffness $S = dF/dh$, where F is the applied force on the sample. The force as a function of indentation depth is considered continuous and differentiable at any point.

Given that the contact stiffness is a known function, the applied force can be easily calculated as follows:

$$F(h) = \int_0^h S(y) dy. \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is generic and valid for any material, homogeneous or not. The only restriction is that $S(y)$ must be an integrable function. When indenting elastic half-spaces, the applied force (Eq. (1)) depends on the material properties (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio) as well as the properties of the indenter (size and shape) [31]. For homogeneous samples with finite thickness, it also depends

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on the sample's thickness [26–29]. More specifically, according to Buckle's rule, if the indentation depth is larger than 5–10% of the sample thickness, then the influence of the substrate leads to a significant overestimation of the Young's modulus [35–37]. In the most general case, “the contact stiffness should also depend on the depth-dependent mechanical properties of the sample.”

AFM nanoindentation is the most widely used method for studying heterogeneous soft samples. However, traditional analysis tools based on Hertzian mechanics cannot quantitatively address the mechanical heterogeneity often observed in biological samples when determining the elastic modulus from indentation experiments. In recent years, there has been significant focus on developing new mathematical models and equations to account for the mechanical heterogeneity of soft samples. In particular, Amo *et al.* demonstrated that bimodal AFM enables the accurate measurement of the elastic modulus of surfaces in liquid with a spatial resolution of 3 Å [38]. Doss *et al.* developed an analytical model to process force-indentation data for 2-layered elastic materials [39]. It was found that the effect of the underlying layer can be predicted. This effect is analogous to the Hookean springs in series. The model is accurate for up to a 2-order magnitude mismatch in Young's modulus when the contact radius is smaller than the layer height [39]. In addition, very recently, Chen *et al.* proposed a robust strategy, termed trimechanic theory, to encompass the elastic behaviors of soft materials and biomaterials under various conditions [40]. Changes in elastic behaviors reflect alterations in the material's context. Trimechanic theory enables the quantification of differences in elastic responses through various combinations of 3 nanomechanical actions, which are governed by constant, linear and non-linear forces, respectively [40]. It arises naturally from the extension of Sneddon's pyramid model for the investigation of elastic heterogeneity [40]. Other works focus on extending the applicability of the equations derived from Hertzian mechanics to heterogeneous samples when using cylindrical, parabolic, conical, spherical and arbitrarily shaped axisymmetric indenters for $h/H \rightarrow 0$, where h is the indentation depth and H is the sample's thickness at the point of measurement [41, 42]. In this way, 3D nanomechanical characterization of soft heterogeneous samples can be easily achieved [41]. Therefore, it has already been shown that for highly heterogeneous samples with “infinite depth” (i.e. when the sample's height is significantly greater than the indentation depth), Hertzian equations can be extended to provide depth-dependent mechanical properties.

In addition, an interesting method for comprehensive spatial nanocharacterization of soft biological samples at the microscale has recently been developed, utilizing acoustic manipulation and force microscopy [43]. Specifically, a device driven by acoustic manipulation, equipped with a micro-force sensor, has been developed to enable the free rotation of biological samples and quantify their mechanical properties across multiple regions. The trapping of samples and their reorientation relative to the force sensor is facilitated by acoustic streaming generated through the excitation of trapped microbubbles [43].

Despite significant scientific efforts to develop accurate mathematical models for characterizing soft heterogeneous samples, there remain unexplored cases, such as heterogeneous samples with finite thickness. Accurate mathematical models have previously been developed to address the finite thickness of samples, but they do not consider the sample's heterogeneity. Therefore, in this paper, the latter general case will be considered. The primary goal is to use the generic Eq. (1) to derive force-indentation equations that can be easily applied to determine the depth-dependent mechanical properties of thin heterogeneous samples on rigid substrates, and to evaluate these equations using real experimental data. The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 generalizes the equations used for homogeneous samples with finite thickness for cases where heterogeneity cannot be ignored. Section 3 is the “Materials and Methods” section, where the protocols used for AFM nanoindentation experiments on cells (human fibroblasts and murine cancer cells) and the method for processing data to account for depth-dependent mechanical properties are presented. Section 4 is the “Results” section. The depth-dependent mechanical properties of cells are presented, and the results are evaluated by comparing them to different approaches from the literature focused on cell mechanics. Special attention is also given to explaining the physical significance of the parameters related to the determination of depth-dependent mechanical properties.

2. CHARACTERIZATION OF HETEROGENEOUS SAMPLES WITH FINITE THICKNESS

2.1 A brief presentation for homogeneous materials

For a homogeneous sample with finite thickness, the applied force by the indenter (F) is related to the indentation depth (h) and the sample's thickness (H) as follows [26–28]:

$$F = F_{\text{Hertz}} f(h, H). \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), F_{Hertz} corresponds to the classic Hertzian equations for an elastic half-space, and $f(h, H)$ is a function of the indentation depth and the sample's finite thickness. For $h/H \rightarrow 0$, $f(h, H) \rightarrow 1$. For axisymmetric indenters, Eq. (1) can be also written as follows [26–28]:

$$F = ah^n f(h, H). \quad (3)$$

Typical pyramidal indenters are usually approximated to perfect cones in AFM indentation experiments [27]. Considering that the Poisson's ratio of the heterogeneous sample is $\nu \cong 0.5$ due to the high water content [28], for conical indenters $a = \frac{8}{3\pi} E \tan(\theta)$ and $n = 2$ [7]. The function $f(h, H)$ is a polynomial [27, 28]:

$$f(h, H) = 1 + c_1 \frac{h}{H} + c_2 \left(\frac{h}{H}\right)^2 + \dots \quad (4)$$

The coefficients c_1, c_2, \dots depend on the cone's half-angle and whether the sample is bonded to the substrate or not. Gavara and Chadwick derived a generic equation valid for any cone's half angle [28]. According to their equation, $c_1 = \beta \frac{2 \tan(\theta)}{\pi^2}$ and $c_2 = 16\beta^2 \tan^2(\theta)$, where $\beta = 1.7795$ for adherent and $\beta = 0.388$ for non-adherent samples. Higher-order terms are neglected in this model. Another approach for conical indenters has been proposed by Santos *et al.* [27]. For non-bonded samples to the substrate, with semi-angles in the range of $60^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$, $c_1 = 0.2664 \tan(\theta)$, $c_2 = 1.173 \tan^2(\theta)$, $c_3 = -0.98 \tan^3(\theta)$ and $c_4 = 0.5168 \tan^4(\theta)$. For bonded samples to the substrate, $c_1 = 0.6298 \tan(\theta)$, $c_2 = 0.7236 \tan^2(\theta)$, $c_3 = 1.249 \tan^3(\theta)$ and $c_4 = -0.3556 \tan^4(\theta)$. Other expressions for flat punch and parabolic indenters can also be found in [29]. By combining Eqs. (3) and (4), it can be readily concluded:

$$F = a \left(h^n + \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n+1} + \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^{n+2} + \dots \right). \quad (5)$$

The contact stiffness at an arbitrary depth h and for a sample with a given thickness H should be:

$$S = \frac{dF}{dh} = a \left[n h^{n-1} + (n+1) \frac{c_1}{H} h^n + \frac{c_2}{H^2} (n+2) h^{n+1} + \dots \right]. \quad (6)$$

2.2 Extending the equations for heterogeneous materials

Eqs. (3)–(6) have been derived under the assumption that a remains constant regardless of the values of the indentation depth h . Therefore, when fitting the force-indentation data to Eq. (5), the parameter a can be easily determined, which allows for the calculation of the Young's modulus of the sample, provided that the sample's Poisson's ratio and thickness are known.

Consider an alternative case in which the parameter a in Eq. (6) is depth-dependent. Therefore, consider an appropriate function $a(h)$ to describe the mechanical properties of the arbitrarily heterogeneous sample:

$$S(h) = a(h) \left[n h^{n-1} + (n+1) \frac{c_1}{H} h^n + \frac{c_2}{H^2} (n+2) h^{n+1} + \dots \right]. \quad (7)$$

The function $a(h)$ should have the appropriate form so that, when substituted into Eq. (7), Eq. (1) will yield the force-indentation function that is recorded during the actual experiment. Therefore, Eq. (1) yields:

$$F = \int_0^h S(y) dy = \int_0^h a(y) \left[n y^{n-1} + (n+1) \frac{c_1}{H} y^n + \frac{c_2}{H^2} (n+2) y^{n+1} + \dots \right] dy = \int_0^h a(y) g(y) dy. \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8),

$$g(y) = n y^{n-1} + (n+1) \frac{c_1}{H} y^n + \frac{c_2}{H^2} (n+2) y^{n+1} + \dots \quad (9)$$

To proceed further from Eq. (9), the weighted mean value theorem for integrals will be used [44]. Let $a, g: [0, h] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be such that a is continuous and g is integrable and does not change the sign on $[0, h]$. Then, there exists a number $c \in (0, h)$ such that:

$$\int_0^h a(y) g(y) dy = \alpha(c) \int_0^h g(y) dy. \quad (10)$$

Therefore, using Eqs. (9) and (10), Eq. (8) is modified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \alpha(c) \int_0^h \left[n y^{n-1} + (n+1) \frac{c_1}{H} y^n + \frac{c_2}{H^2} (n+2) y^{n+1} + \dots \right] dy \Rightarrow \\ F &= \alpha(c) \left(h^n + \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n+1} + \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^{n+2} + \dots \right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In addition, if $y \in (0, h)$ it is possible to choose a number $0 < c_y < y$ as a function of y on $(0, h)$ such that [44]:

$$\int_0^y a(u) g(u) du = \alpha(c_y) \int_0^y g(u) du. \quad (12)$$

In Eq. (12), u is a dummy integration parameter. Therefore,

$$F = \alpha(c_y) \left(y^n + \frac{c_1}{H} y^{n+1} + \frac{c_2}{H^2} y^{n+2} + \dots \right), \text{ where } y < h. \quad (13)$$

The function $\alpha(c_y)$ is depth dependent and provides the mechanical properties of heterogeneous samples for an arbitrary indentation depth $y < h$. Eq. (13) accounts for the sample's heterogeneity and the sample's finite thickness. The parameter $\alpha(c_y)$ depends also on the indenter's geometry. Therefore, for conical indenters:

$$\alpha(c_y) = \frac{8}{3\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta). \quad (14)$$

The parameter $E(c_y)$ is not constant; therefore, it cannot be considered the sample's Young's modulus in the classical sense. To provide a better first clarification regarding $E(c_y)$, consider the following: let us assume a function E that provides the exact Young's modulus of any specific internal nanoregion at an arbitrary depth y . The $E(c_y)$ should be an "equivalent" or "average value" of this function which accounts for the overall mechanical properties of the tested material for an arbitrary indentation depth y . In other words, in Eq. (14), c_y is an arbitrary number (where $0 < c_y < y$) of the function E such that the value $E(c_y)$ is a representative magnitude for the mechanical properties in the domain $0 < \text{indentation depth} < y$. Therefore, $E(c_y)$ is depth dependent. Considering that the maximum indentation depth in a specific experiment is h , then, the overall properties of the material are represented by the value $E(c_h)$. Therefore for conical indenters, the data can be fitted to the following equation [28]:

$$F(y) = \frac{8}{3\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) y^2 \left[1 + 1.7795 \frac{2 \tan(\theta) y}{\pi^2 H} + 16(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \left(\frac{y}{H}\right)^2 + O\left(\frac{y^3}{H^3}\right) \right]. \quad (15)$$

The approach proposed in this paper is valid for any model in the literature that uses correction functions represented as polynomial series to account for the substrate effect. The number of terms is determined by the specific model. For example, the Gavara and Chadwick model is expressed in the form of equation [15]. In this case, there are only 3 terms. This is because the notation O (often referred to as "big O notation") indicates that the remaining terms are of a smaller order and are considered negligible for the purposes of approximation. This means that these terms do not significantly affect the result within the specified context, particularly as the variable approaches a certain limit. In their experiment, they tested the equation above for very large indentation depths (up to $h/H = 0.85$) [28]. Therefore, Eq. (15) can be simplified as follows:

$$F(y) = \frac{8}{3\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) y^2 \left[1 + 1.7795 \frac{2 \tan(\theta) y}{\pi^2 H} + 16(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \left(\frac{y}{H}\right)^2 \right]. \quad (16)$$

The model proposed by Santos *et al.* uses 5 terms in their polynomial expressions and is valid for $\frac{ht \tan \theta}{H} < 0.8$ [27]. It is also important to note that for a regular 4-sided pyramidal AFM tip, the force—indentation equation for an elastic half space (considering $\nu \cong 0.5$) is [27]:

$$F_{pyr.} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{2}} E \tan(\theta) h^2 \cong 1.11 F_{cone}. \quad (17)$$

Since the force—indentation relationships for both pyramidal and conical indenters share the same exponent ($n = 2$), the pyramidal geometry is usually treated as a conical one, resulting in $F_{pyr.} \cong 1.11 F_{cone}$ [27]. Therefore, for 4-sided regular pyramids:

$$F(y) = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{2}} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) y^2 \left[1 + 1.7795 \frac{2 \tan(\theta) y}{\pi^2 H} + 16(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \left(\frac{y}{H}\right)^2 \right]. \quad (18)$$

The same analysis can be also performed for spherical indentations. In this case, for homogeneous materials, the force—indentation function is presented below:

$$F = a \left(h^n + \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n+1/2} + \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^{n+1} + \dots \right). \quad (19)$$

In Eq. (19), $\alpha = \frac{16}{9} ER^{1/2}$. Therefore, the contact stiffness can be easily calculated as follows:

$$S = \frac{dF}{dh} = a \left[nh^{n-1} + \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n-1/2} + (n+1) \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^n + \dots \right]. \quad (20)$$

For a sample not bonded to the substrate $c_1 = 0.884R^{1/2}$, $c_2 = 0.781R$, $c_3 = 0.386R^{3/2}$ and $c_4 = 0.0084R^2$ [26]. When the sample is bonded to the substrate $c_1 = 1.133R^{1/2}$, $c_2 = 1.283R$, $c_3 = 0.769R^{3/2}$ and $c_4 = 0.0975R^2$ [26]. In the case of a material with depth-dependent mechanical properties, the contact stiffness is provided below:

$$S(h) = a(h) \left[nh^{n-1} + \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n-1/2} + (n+1) \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^n + \dots \right]. \quad (21)$$

For materials with depth-dependent mechanical properties, the parameter a is a function of the indentation depth. Therefore,

$$F = \int_0^h S(y) dy = \int_0^h a(y) \left[nh^{n-1} + \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n-1/2} + (n+1) \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^n + \dots \right] dy. \quad (22)$$

Using the weighted mean value theorem it is concluded:

$$F = \alpha(c_y) \left(h^n + \frac{c_1}{H} h^{n+1/2} + \frac{c_2}{H^2} h^{n+1} + \dots \right), \quad (23)$$

where,

$$\alpha(c_y) = \frac{16}{9} E(c_y) R^{1/2}. \quad (24)$$

The model by Dimitriadis *et al.* uses 5 terms in their polynomial expressions [26, 27]. Finite element analysis has shown that it can be safely applied for $\sqrt{Rh}/H < 0.5$ [27].

Equations (15), (16), (18), (23), (24) simply demonstrate that it is mathematically accurate to test heterogeneous samples with finite thickness using the classic equations derived for homogeneous materials. Nevertheless, in this case, the fitting parameter equals $E(c_y)$ for a specific indentation depth y . In other words, $E(c_y)$ can be used to represent the sample's mechanical properties only for the aforementioned indentation depth. When changing the fitting domain (e.g. $0 < y < y'$) the $E(c_y)$ parameter also results differently. Consequently, the depth-dependent mechanical properties of heterogeneous samples can only be described by a set of values as follows: (y_1, y_2, \dots, h) , $[E(c_{y1}), E(c_{y2}), \dots, E(c_{h})]$. This set of values can be used to derive a function $\varepsilon = f(y)$ to represent the depth-dependent mechanical properties.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Open access AFM data from fibroblasts

Open access nanoindentation data obtained using a conical indenter on human fibroblasts was utilized [45]. According to this paper, human fibroblasts were cultured and maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. In addition, an AFM tip (Veeco Probes) with a nominal tip radius of 20 nm, a half-angle of 25°, and a spring constant of 0.01 N/m was used [45]. The force-indentation curves that were used showed significant deviations from the linear elastic model for conical indenters. Therefore, the contact point identification was performed using a “robust successive search method” as described in [45]. In addition, curves with large indentation depths were used to ensure the substrate effect. The force-indentation data employed in this study are deposited in the AtomicJ repository:

(<https://sourceforge.net/projects/jrobust/files/TestFiles/>).

3.2. AFM experiments on cancer cells

3.2.1 Cell culturing

Murine breast cancer cell lines E0771 were obtained from American Type Culture Collection and were incubated at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator. The cells were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% antibiotics [46].

3.2.2 AFM measurements

AFM experiments were performed with a commercial AFM (5500 Keysight technologies) using the MLCT Bio (cantilever C) tip manufactured by Bruker. The nominal tip radius was 20 nm, the half-angle was 35°, and the spring constant was 0.01 N/m [47]. Cells were cultured on 35 mm petri dishes and were mounted directly on the AFM stage. Calibration of the spring constant was achieved through the utilization of the thermal noise method, while the sensitivity calibration was obtained by obtaining force-versus-distance curves on a petri dish, which is a pristine, rigid surface [48]. The applied force was set to 1 nN, and force curves were acquired for each specimen over an area of $5 \mu\text{m}^2$ at the center of the cell (this area was selected using the optical system that accompanies the AFM) [49]. In addition, curves with large indentation depths were used to ensure the substrate effect.

3.3 Determining the depth dependent mechanical properties

Cells are considered to be bonded to the substrate; therefore, Eq. (16) was used for data processing. In this section, the strategy for determining the $E(c_y)$ parameter for different indentation depths will be presented. The work done by the indenter for an arbitrary indentation depth y is equal to the area under the force-indentation curve [50]. Since $E(c_y)$ is a constant parameter for a specific domain:

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int_0^y F du = \frac{8}{3\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) \int_0^y \left(u^2 + 1.7795 \frac{2 \tan(\theta)}{\pi^2} \frac{u^3}{H} + 16(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \frac{u^4}{H^2} \right) du \\ &= \frac{8}{3\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) \left[\frac{y^3}{3} + 1.7795 \frac{2 \tan(\theta)}{\pi^2} \frac{y^4}{4H} + 16(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \frac{y^5}{5H^2} \right] \\ &= \frac{8}{9\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) y^3 \left[1 + 1.7795 \frac{6 \tan(\theta)}{\pi^2} \frac{y}{4H} + 48(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \frac{y^2}{5H^2} \right] \\ W &= \frac{8}{9\pi} E(c_y) \tan(\theta) y^3 \Lambda \left(\frac{y}{H} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

In Eq. (25),

$$\Lambda \left(\frac{y}{H} \right) = 1 + 1.7795 \frac{6 \tan(\theta)}{\pi^2} \frac{y}{4H} + 48(1.7795)^2 \tan^2(\theta) \frac{y^2}{5H^2}. \quad (26)$$

Figure 1 (a) The $\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right)$ function in the domain $0 < \frac{y}{H} < 0.5$ ($\theta = 25^\circ$). (b) The percentage differences between the $E(c_y)$ parameter calculated using Eq. (25) and the infinite thickness approximation ($\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right) \rightarrow 1$). For $\frac{y}{H} > 0.1$ sample appears significantly “stiffer” when its thickness is ignored.

For example, for $\theta = 25^\circ$,

$$\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right) = 1 + 0.1260\frac{y}{H} + 6.6014\frac{y^2}{H^2}. \quad (27)$$

In Fig. 1(a), the $\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right)$ function for $0 < \frac{y}{H} < 0.5$ and $\theta = 25^\circ$ is presented. For a material with infinite thickness $\frac{y}{H} \rightarrow 0$ and $\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right) \rightarrow 1$. The percentage difference in the $E(c_y)$ parameter calculated using Eq. (25) and the infinite thickness approximation can be easily determined as shown below (Fig. 1(b)):

$$\pi(\%) = \frac{E(c_y)_{thin\ sample} - E(c_y)_{inf.\ thickness}}{E(c_y)_{thin\ sample}} \times 100\% = \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{y}{H}\right) - 1 \right] \times 100\%. \quad (28)$$

The $E(c_y)$ parameter was calculated 10 times for each force-indentation curve using Eq. (25) for different domains. Specifically, consider that the maximum indentation depth equals h . The first calculation is performed in the domain $0 < y < \frac{h}{10}$, resulting in $E_1(c_{y1})$. The second is performed for $0 < y < \frac{h}{5}$ resulting in $E_2(c_{y2})$. The procedure is also repeated 8 times for each curve. The last calculation is performed for the entire domain, $0 < y < h$, resulting in $E_{10}(c_h)$. Subsequently the $(y, E(c_y))$ data were fitted to appropriate functions in MATLAB to determine the material’s depth-dependent mechanical properties. In other words, the function $E(c_y) = f(y)$ can reveal either hardening or softening behavior of the tested material.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 presents 5 representative force indentation curves obtained on a fibroblast, processed using the method described in Section 3.3. More specifically, Fig. 2i(a–e) show the force-indentation curves at 5 different points, where the thickness of the cell was approximately $2\ \mu\text{m}$. The exact thickness of the cell in the region of the measurements was determined using the AFM topographical image that accompanies the open-access force indentation data in the AtomicJ repository [45]. The maximum indentation depth for these curves was approximately 550–750 nm. Therefore, according to Eqs. (27) and (28), the error if using the classic Sneddon’s

Figure 2 (i) (a–e). Five force-indentation curves obtained from a fibroblast. The cell’s thickness at the location of the experiments was approximately $2 \mu\text{m}$. (ii) (a–e). The area under each force indentation curve was determined for 10 different indentation depths. (iii) (a–e) The results presented in Figures (ii) (a–e) were used to calculate the parameter $E(c_y)$ for each indentation depth. The y , $E(c_y)$ data was fitted to an appropriate exponential function with accuracy.

Figure 3 (a) A force—indentation curve on murine breast cancer cell. (b) The area under the force indentation curve was determined for 10 different indentation depths. (c) The results presented in Figure (b) were used to calculate the parameter $E(c_y)$ for each indentation depth. The y , $E(c_y)$ data was fitted to an appropriate exponential function with accuracy. (d) A topographical image of the cell. The thickness of the cell at the center is approximately $4.7 \mu\text{m}$.

equation for conical indenters will be in the range ~ 53 – 98% . Consequently, Eqs. (25) and (27) were used for data processing instead of the classic Sneddon equation. In Fig. 2ii(a–e) the work done by the indenter for 10 different indentation depths (i.e. $y_1 = \frac{h}{10}$, $y_2 = \frac{h}{5}$, \dots , $y_{10} = h$) is presented. In Fig. 2iii(a–e), the $E(c_y)$ parameter for 10 different indentation depths is calculated using the results presented in Fig. 2ii(a–e) and Eqs. (25) and (27). Figure 3(a)–(c) also presents a representative measurement of a murine breast cancer cell. The maximum indentation depth in the measurement region (at an area in the center of the cell, as described in Section 3.2.2) was approximately $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, while the cell's thickness at the same point was approximately $4.7 \mu\text{m}$. A topographical image of the cell is also shown in Fig. 3(d). The data in every case follow an exponential law of the form:

$$\varepsilon(y) = Ay^B + C, \quad \text{where } A, C > 0 \text{ and } B < 0. \quad (29)$$

According to Ding *et al.*, AFM measurements on cells are significantly affected by surface tension [33]. Using dimensional analysis and finite element simulations, they have shown that when testing a cell with a conical indenter (for $y/H \rightarrow 0$), the force indentation data follow the law [33]:

$$F(y) = \frac{2 E_{app.}(y)}{\pi} \frac{1}{1 - \nu^2} \tan(\theta) y^2. \quad (30)$$

In Eq. (30), $E_{app.}(y)$ is the apparent Young's modulus, which is provided below:

$$E_{app.}(y) = E + a_c E \left[\frac{s}{y \tan(\theta)} \right]^{\beta_c} \quad (31)$$

Figure 4 (a) A force-indentation curve on a heterogeneous thin sample on a rigid substrate. The area under the graph equals the work (W) done by the indenter. The material properties for a specific indentation depth y can be determined by the depth-dependent parameter $E(c_y)$. (b) A force-indentation curve on a homogeneous thin sample, considering the same indenter, indentation depth, sample thickness and work done by the indenter. In this case, the homogeneous sample will have a Young's modulus E equal to $E(c_y)$.

In Eq. (31), $a_c = 0.95 \pm 0.0097$, $\beta_c = 0.95 \pm 0.0088$ and s is an intrinsic length that surface tension affects and can be estimated using the following equation:

$$s = \frac{2\gamma(1 - \nu^2)}{E}. \quad (32)$$

In Eq. (32), γ is the constant surface energy density measured in mN/m , and E is the “actual” Young's modulus according to Ding *et al.*'s model (i.e. the measured Young's modulus if the surface tension were zero) [33]. Eq. (29) has the same form as Eq. (31) if considering that $E = C$, $|B| = \beta_c$ and $A = a_c E \left[\frac{s}{\tan(\theta)} \right]^{\beta_c}$.

A critical test to evaluate the method presented in this paper is to compare the results with those provided by Eq. (31). In other words, the “corrected equation” (16) should be able to reproduce the same results regarding the cell's behavior when the influence of the substrate on the force-indentation data is not negligible.

To evaluate the ability of Eq. (25) to accurately derive the depth-dependent mechanical properties of cells, the y , $E(c_y)$ data in each case were fitted to Eq. (31), considering as already mentioned $\beta_c = 0.95 \pm 0.0088$. The results in each case are shown in Figs 2iii(a–e) and 3(c). The R-squared coefficient ($R_{s.c.}^2$) was close to 1 in any case. Therefore, despite the strong influence of the rigid substrate, the cell's mechanical behavior was correctly recorded.

However, an important question emerges at this stage. How can the softening behavior of cells as the indentation depth increases be explained? Several studies have shown that the elasticity of cells is closely associated with the cell cytoskeleton, particularly the F-actin fibers [7, 51, 4]. Typically, the cell cytoskeleton consists of F-actin, microtubules and intermediate filaments, each of which is distributed differently within the cell. For instance, short F-actin filaments are situated beneath the cell membrane, whereas F-actin stress fibers, which are bundles of single filaments, extend across the cell body [7]. Conversely, the microtubules, composed of α - and β -tubulins, are found in the region between the nucleus and the cell membrane. Utilizing cytoskeleton drugs, such as cytochalasin D, which depolymerizes actin filaments [52], or microtubule-targeted drugs, has demonstrated that the elastic properties measured by AFM are primarily influenced by actin filaments [4, 53]. Additionally, it has been proposed that microtubules and intermediate filaments do not have a significant impact on AFM measurements of live cells [54, 55]. Moreover, some studies have shown that both the organization of actin filaments and the total amount of actin are important for cellular stiffness [56]. As a result, considering that at low indentation depths (near the cell membrane) both short actin filaments and stress fibers contribute to the measured Young's modulus, whereas at greater indentation depths only the F-actin stress fibers are present, the presented results can be elucidated. At greater indentation depths, the Young's modulus is reduced due to the lack of short F-actin fibers.

It is also interesting to explain the physical significance of the parameter $E(c_y)$ calculated when processing the force-indentation data for a specific indentation depth y . Equations resulting from Hertzian analysis and their extensions for thin materials (Eq. (2)) were initially derived for homogeneous and isotropic materials. In other words, the Young's modulus should be the same regardless of the exact position where the force-indentation curve is obtained and regardless of the indentation depth. For heterogeneous samples, the parameter $E(c_y)$ depends strongly on the location of the experiment and the indentation depth. To provide a “physical significance” to the parameter $E(c_y)$, we can proceed as follows. Consider the case of force-indentation data on a highly heterogeneous material on a rigid substrate using an indenter with a well-known geometry (Fig. 4a). Considering that the force function is continuous and differentiable at any point, and that it is a function of the indentation depth (y), the sample's thickness (H), the material properties

(E) and the indenter geometry (Ω), we obtain:

$$S(y, H, E, \Omega) = \frac{dF(y, H, E, \Omega)}{dy} \Rightarrow F(y, H, E, \Omega) = \int_0^y S(u, H, E, \Omega) du. \quad (33)$$

Regardless of the exact force function, it is trivial to calculate the work done by the indenter because it simply equals the area under the graph.

$$W(y, H, E, \Omega) = \int_0^y F(u, H, E, \Omega) du. \quad (34)$$

To provide a physical significance for the parameter related to the material properties, we can consider an “equivalent” force-indentation curve obtained with the same indenter on a homogeneous and isotropic material with the same thickness, the same maximum indentation depth, and the same area under the $F - y$ curve. In this case,

$$W(y, H, E, \Omega) = E \int_0^y F(u, H, \Omega) du. \quad (35)$$

In Eq. (35), E is the Young’s modulus of the homogeneous and isotropic sample in the “equivalent” experiment. In this paper, it was shown that Eq. (34) can also be written as follows:

$$W(y, H, E, \Omega) = E(c_y) \int_0^y F(u, H, \Omega) du. \quad (36)$$

The parameter $E(c_y)$ is an “equivalent” or “average” Young’s modulus that reflects the overall properties of the sample for an indentation depth of y . By comparing Eqs. (35) and (36), it is concluded that the $E(c_y)$ parameter represents the Young’s modulus of an equivalent experiment on a homogeneous and isotropic sample of finite thickness under the same conditions (i.e. the same indenter, indentation depth, work done by the indenter and sample thickness). This is an important point, as it is evident that characterizing highly heterogeneous samples using the equations derived in this paper is accurate from both a mathematical and physical perspective.

In addition, the $\varepsilon(y)$ functions (e.g. Eq. (29)) also have physical significance. To characterize a highly heterogeneous material, we can consider N equivalent experiments with different indentation depths on homogeneous and isotropic materials of the same thickness H . The first experiment considers an equivalent homogeneous material with an indentation depth equal to y_1 . The resulting Young’s modulus is $E_1 = E(c_{y1})$. The second experiment assumes an equivalent experiment on a homogeneous material with $y_2 > y_1$ and $E_2 = E(c_{y2})$. The last experiment assumes an equivalent experiment on a homogeneous material with $y_N > y_{N-1}$ and $E_y = E(c_{yN})$. Subsequently, the y, E data set can be fitted to appropriate functions to derive a “material properties function” $\varepsilon = f(y)$.

It is also important to note that the method presented in this paper is generic and can be applied to any sample with finite thickness (e.g. collagen thin films [57] and fibrils [58–60]). For example, it is not mandatory to obtain exponential “material properties functions” of the form given in Eq. (29). The reason for conducting experiments on cells is that these materials exhibit a “well-known” mechanical behavior, which makes it feasible to demonstrate the accuracy of the method presented in this paper. As demonstrated, the $\varepsilon = f(y)$ function (Eq. (29)) revealed the influence of surface tension on a conventional force-indentation experiment. This “exponential decrease” of the “apparent” modulus of cells has also been shown using empirical methods in cases with no influence from the substrate [32].

However, it is also important to note that there are two main limitations to the presented work. As mentioned earlier, the model accounts for the depth-dependent heterogeneity of the soft samples. In other words, it is assumed that the mechanical heterogeneity occurs only in the depth-direction (i.e. the direction of the indentation depth) and not in the horizontal plane. To provide a better understanding of this limitation, consider the weighted mean value theorem for integrals. In any case, two functions were considered; one represents a function that depends only on the h/H ratio. For a specific experiment on a sample with a given thickness H , the only variable parameter in this function is the indentation depth. This function is referred to as $g(y)$. The other function is related to the depth-dependent mechanical properties of the sample and is denoted as $E(y)$. Therefore, according to the weighted mean value theorem for integrals:

$$\int_0^h E(y) g(y) dy = E(c) \int_0^h g(y) dy. \quad (37)$$

It is clear that this approach does not account for variabilities in the horizontal plane within the contact area between the indenter and the sample. However, this is not a significant drawback of the method, as the mechanical heterogeneity in the horizontal plane over extended regions can be estimated using multiple measurements at different points to create a mechanical properties map. The only restriction is that, at each specific measurement, the mechanical properties in the horizontal plane within the contact area are considered to be constant, and only the depth-dependent heterogeneity is recorded.

The second restriction pertains to layered materials that consist of layers with significant differences in mechanical properties. For example, consider a two layered material. The Young’s moduli of these layers are E_1 and E_2 , with their values being significantly

different. The depth dependent Young's modulus function in this case is:

$$E(h) = \begin{cases} E_1, & 0 \leq h < h_1 \\ E_2, & h_1 < h \leq h_2 \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

In Eq. (38), h_1 denotes the thickness of the first layer, while the thickness of the second layer is given by $d = h_2 - h_1$. According to the mean value theorem for integrals, the function $E(h)$ should be continuous. In other words, the proposed approach is accurate for materials in which the mechanical properties change smoothly as the indentation depth increases. For layered materials, where each layer presents significant differences from its neighboring layer (which is typically the case for 2-layered materials), the method cannot be applied. However, for the special case of 2-layered materials, an accurate model has already been developed [39].

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the force-indentation equations for homogeneous materials with finite thickness are generalized for heterogeneous materials. In addition, a new method is presented to derive the mechanical properties of such materials in relation to indentation depth. The proposed model is applied to human fibroblasts and murine breast cancer cells and successfully reveals their mechanical patterns. Therefore, this paper may evolve into a useful tool for acquiring reproducible results when conducting experiments on highly heterogeneous materials using AFM.

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REFERENCES

- Lekka M, Laidler P. Applicability of AFM in cancer detection. *Nature Nanotechnology* 2009;**4**(2):72.
- Plodinec M, Loparic M, Monnier CA, Obermann EC, Zanetti-Dallenbach R, Oertle P, Hyotyla JT, Aebi U, Bentires-Alj M, Lim RYH, Schoenberger CA. The nanomechanical signature of breast cancer. *Nature Nanotechnology* 2012;**7**(11):757–765.
- Stylianou A, Lekka M, Stylianopoulos T. AFM assessing of nanomechanical fingerprints for cancer early diagnosis and classification: from single cell to tissue level. *Nanoscale* 2018;**10**(45):20930–20945.
- Stylianou A, Gkretsi V, Stylianopoulos T. Transforming growth factor- β modulates pancreatic cancer-associated fibroblasts cell shape, stiffness, and invasion. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)—General Subjects* 2018;**1862**(7):1537–1546.
- Stylianou A, Kontomaris SV, Alexandratou E, Grant C. Atomic force microscopy on biological materials related to pathological conditions. *Scanning* 2019;**45**:8452851.
- Lekka M, Gil D, Pogoda K, Dulińska-Litewka J, Jach R, Gostek J, Laidler P. Cancer cell detection in tissue sections using AFM. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* 2012;**518**(2):151–156.
- Lekka M. Discrimination between normal and cancerous cells using AFM. *BioNanoScience* 2016;**6**(1):65–80.
- Zemla J, Danilkiewicz J, Orzechowska B, Pabijan J, Seweryn S, Lekka M. Atomic force microscopy as a tool for assessing the cellular elasticity and adhesiveness to identify cancer cells and tissues. *Seminars in Cell & Developmental Biology* 2018;**73**:115–124.
- Cross SE, Jin Y-S, Tondre J, Wong R, Rao J, Gimzewski JK. AFM-based analysis of human metastatic cancer cells. *Nanotechnology* 2008;**19**(38):384003.
- Holuigue H, Lorenc E, Chighizola M, Schulte C, Varinelli L, Deraco M, Guaglio M, Gariboldi M, Podestà A. Force sensing on cells and tissues by atomic force microscopy. *Sensors* 2022;**22**(6):2197.
- Ludwig T, Kirmse R, Poole K, Schwarz US Probing cellular microenvironments and tissue remodeling by atomic force microscopy. *Pflügers Archiv—European Journal of Physiology* 2008;**456**(1):29–49.
- Hayashi K, Iwata M. Stiffness of cancer cells measured with an AFM indentation method. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials* 2015;**49**:105–111.
- Sokolov I, Dokukin ME, Guz NV. Method for quantitative measurements of the elastic modulus of biological cells in AFM indentation experiments. *Methods (San Diego, Calif)* 2013;**60**(2):202–213.
- Viji Babu PK, Radmacher M. Mechanics of brain tissues studied by atomic force microscopy: a perspective. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 2019;**13**:600.
- Jorba I, Uriarte JJ, Campillo N, Farré R, Navajas D. Probing micromechanical properties of the extracellular matrix of soft tissues by atomic force microscopy. *Journal of Cellular Physiology* 2017;**232**(1):19–26.
- Gautier HOB, Thompson AJ, Achouri S, Koser DE, Holtzmann K, Moendarbary E, Franze K. Atomic force microscopy-based force measurements on animal cells and tissues. *Biophysical Methods in Cell Biology* 2015;**125**:211–235.
- Abidine Y, Constantinescu A, Laurent VM, Rajan VS, Michel R, Laplaud V, Duperray A, Verdier C. Mechanosensitivity of cancer cells in contact with soft substrates using AFM. *Biophysical Journal* 2018;**114**(5):1165–1175.
- Liu S, Han Y, Kong L, Wang G, Ye Z. Atomic force microscopy in disease-related studies: exploring tissue and cell mechanics. *Microscopy Research and Technique* 2023;**87**(4):660–684.
- Zhou G, Zhang B, Tang G, Yu XF, Galluzzi M. Cells nanomechanics by atomic force microscopy: focus on interactions at the nanoscale. *Advances in Physics: X* 2021;**6**(1):1–31.
- Liang W, Shi H, Yang X, Wang J, Yang W, Zhang H, Liu L. Recent advances in AFM-based biological characterizations and applications at multiple levels. *Soft Matter* 2020;**16**(39):8962–8984.

21. Kiio TM, Park S. Nano-scientific application of atomic force microscopy in pathology: from molecules to tissues. *International Journal of Medical Sciences* 2020;**17**(7):844–858.
22. Calò A, Romin Y, Srouji R, Zambirinis CP, Fan N, Santella A, Feng E, Fujisawa S, Turkekel M, Huang S, Simpson AL. Spatial mapping of the collagen distribution in human and mouse tissues by force volume atomic force microscopy. *Scientific Reports* 2020;**10**(1):15664.
23. Ihnatouski M, Pauk J, Karev D, Karev B. AFM-based method for measurement of normal and osteoarthritic human articular cartilage surface roughness. *Materials* 2020;**13**(10):2302.
24. Stolz M, Gottardi R, Raiteri R, Miot S, Martin I, Imer R, Stauffer U, Raducanu A, Düggelin M, Baschong W, Daniels AU. Early detection of aging cartilage and osteoarthritis in mice and patient samples using atomic force microscopy. *Nature Nanotechnology* 2009;**4**(3):186–192.
25. Loparic M, Wirz D, Daniels AU, Raiteri R, Vanlandingham MR, Guex G, Martin I, Aebi U, Stolz M. Micro- and nanomechanical analysis of articular cartilage by indentation-type atomic force microscopy: validation with a gel-microfiber composite. *Biophysical Journal* 2010;**98**(11):2731–2740.
26. Dimitriadis EK, Horkay F, Maresca J, Kachar B, Chadwick RS. Determination of elastic moduli of thin layers of soft material using the atomic force microscope. *Biophysical Journal* 2002;**82**(5):2798–2810.
27. Santos JAC, Rebêlo LM, Araujo AC, Barros EB, de Sousa JS. Thickness-corrected model for nanoindentation of thin films with conical indenters. *Soft Matter* 2012;**8**(16):4441.
28. Gavara N, Chadwick RS. Determination of the elastic moduli of thin samples and adherent cells using conical atomic force microscope tips. *Nature Nanotechnology* 2012;**7**(11):733–736.
29. Garcia PD, Garcia R. Determination of the elastic moduli of a single cell cultured on a rigid support by force microscopy. *Biophysical Journal* 2018;**114**(12):2923–2932.
30. Schillers H, Rianna C, Schape J, Luque T, Doschke H, Wälte M, Uriarte JJ, Campillo N, Michanetzis GP, Bobrowska J, Dumitru A. Standardized nanomechanical atomic force microscopy procedure (SNAP) for measuring soft and biological samples. *Scientific Reports* 2017;**7**(1):5117.
31. Krieg M, Flaschner G, Alsteens D, Gaub BM, Roos WH, Wuite GJL, Gaub HE, Gerber C, Dufrêne YF, Müller DJ. Atomic force microscopy-based mechanobiology. *Nature Reviews Physics* 2019;**1**(1):41–57.
32. Pogoda K, Jaczewska J, Wiltowska-Zuber J, Klymenko O, Zuber K, Fornal M, Lekka M. Depth-sensing analysis of cytoskeleton organization based on AFM data. *European Biophysics Journal* 2012;**41**(1):79–87.
33. Ding Y, Wang J, Xu GK, Wang GF. Are elastic moduli of biological cells depth dependent or not? Another explanation using a contact mechanics model with surface tension. *Soft Matter* 2018;**14**(36):7534–7541.
34. Kontomaris SV, Georgakopoulos A, Malamou A, Stylianou A. The average Young's modulus as a physical quantity for describing the depth-dependent mechanical properties of cells. *Mechanics of Materials* 2021;**158**:103846.
35. Baldwin SJ, Sampson J, Peacock CJ, Martin ML, Veres SP, Lee JM, Kreplak L. A new longitudinal variation in the structure of collagen fibrils and its relationship to locations of mechanical damage susceptibility. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials* 2020;**110**:103849.
36. Porsch G, Born C, Utesch B. Nano-hardness investigations of thin films by an atomic force microscope. *Microelectronic Engineering* 1994;**24**(1–4):113–121.
37. Stolz M, Raiteri R, Daniels AU, VanLandingham MR, Baschong W, Aebi U. Dynamic elastic modulus of porcine articular cartilage determined at two different levels of tissue organization by indentation-type atomic force microscopy. *Biophysical Journal* 2004;**86**(5):3269–3283.
38. Amo CA, Perrino AP, Payam AF, Garcia R. Mapping elastic properties of heterogeneous materials in liquid with angstrom-scale resolution. *ACS Nano* 2017;**11**(9):8650–8659.
39. Doss BL, Rahmani Eliato K, Lind KH, Ros R. Quantitative mechanical analysis of indentations on layered, soft elastic materials. *Soft Matter* 2019;**15**(8):1776–1784.
40. Chen SW, Teulon J-M, Kaur H, Godon C, Pellequer J-L. Nano-structural stiffness measure for soft biomaterials of heterogeneous elasticity. *Nanoscale Horizons* 2023;**8**(1):75–82.
41. Kontomaris SV, Stylianou A, Georgakopoulos A, Malamou A. 3D AFM nanomechanical characterization of biological materials. *Nanomaterials* 2023;**13**(3):395.
42. Kontomaris SV, Stylianou A, Chliveros G, Malamou A. AFM indentation on highly heterogeneous materials using different indenter geometries. *Applied Mechanics* 2023;**4**(2):460–475.
43. Läubli NF, Burri JT, Marquard J, Vogler H, Mosca G, Vertti-Quintero N, Shamsudhin N, de Mello A, Grossniklaus U, Ahmed D, Nelson BJ. 3D mechanical characterization of single cells and small organisms using acoustic manipulation and force microscopy. *Nature Communications* 2021;**12**(1):2583.
44. Polezzi M. On the weighted mean value theorem for integrals. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology* 2006;**37**(7):868–870.
45. Hermanowicz P, Sarna M, Burda K, Gabryś H. An open source software for analysis of force curves. *Review of Scientific Instruments* 2014;**85**(6):063703.
46. Stylianou A, Mpekris F, Voutouri C, Papoui A, Constantinidou A, Kiriis E, Kailides M, Stylianopoulos T. Nanomechanical properties of solid tumors as treatment monitoring biomarkers. *Acta Biomaterialia* 2022;**154**:324–334.
47. Stylianou A, Gkretsi V, Louca M, Zacharia LC, Stylianopoulos T. Collagen content and extracellular matrix stiffness remodels pancreatic fibroblasts cytoskeleton. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* 2019;**16**(154):20190226.
48. Stylianou A, Gkretsi V, Patrickios CS, Stylianopoulos T. Exploring the nano-surface of collagenous and other fibrotic tissues with AFM. In: Rittié L, editor. *Fibrosis: Methods and Protocols*. New York: Springer; 2017. p. 453–489.
49. Stylianou A, Voutouri C, Mpekris F, Stylianopoulos T. Pancreatic cancer presents distinct nanomechanical properties during progression. *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 2023;**51**(7):1602–1615.
50. Kontomaris SV, Malamou A, Stylianou A. The Hertzian theory in AFM nanoindentation experiments regarding biological samples: overcoming limitations in data processing. *Micron* 2022;**155**:103228.
51. Grady ME, Composto RJ, Eckmann DM. Cell elasticity with altered cytoskeletal architectures across multiple cell types. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials* 2016;**61**:197–207.
52. Rotsch C, Radmacher M. Drug-induced changes of cytoskeletal structure and mechanics in fibroblasts: an atomic force microscopy study. *Biophysical Journal* 2000;**78**(1):520–535.
53. Radmacher M. Studying the mechanics of cellular processes by atomic force microscopy. In: *Methods in Cell Biology*. Elsevier: Amsterdam, Netherlands; 2007. p. 347–372.

54. Takai E, Costa KD, Shaheen A, Hung CT, Guo XE. Osteoblast elastic modulus measured by atomic force microscopy is substrate dependent. *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 2005;**33**(7):963–971.
55. Titushkin I, Cho M. Modulation of cellular mechanics during osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells. *Biophysical Journal* 2007;**93**(10):3693–3702.
56. Efremov YM, Dokrunova AA, Efremenko AV, Kirpichnikov MP, Shaitan KV, Sokolova OS. Distinct impact of targeted actin cytoskeleton reorganization on mechanical properties of normal and malignant cells. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta Molecular Cell Research* 2015;**1853**:3117–3125.
57. Stylianou A, Kontomaris SV, Yova D. Assessing collagen nanoscale thin films heterogeneity by AFM multimode imaging and nanoindentation for nanobiomedical applications. *Micro and Nanosystems* 2014;**6**(2):95–102.
58. Grant CA, Brockwell DJ, Radford SE, Thomson NH. Effects of hydration on the mechanical response of individual collagen fibrils. *Applied Physics Letters* 2008;**92**(23):233902.
59. Wenger MPE, Bozec L, Horton MA, Mesquidaz P. Mechanical properties of collagen fibrils. *Biophysical Journal* 2007;**93**(4):1255–1263.
60. Heim AJ, Matthews WG, Koob TJ. Determination of the elastic modulus of native collagen fibrils via radial indentation. *Applied Physics Letters* 2006;**89**(18):181902.